

Augmenting LLMs with Knowledge Seeds for Clinical Question Generation

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Outline

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Clinical Assessment in High-Stakes Settings

- Which latent constructs are targeted for measurement?
- High-stakes clinical assessment → clinical judgement skills
- The six functions from NCSBN Clinical Judgement Model (NCJMM):

Problem Statement

- Item development is complex and time-consuming
 - Complexity of clinical reasoning
 - Simulating real-world scenarios
 - Ensuring validity and reliability
- Item bank requires continuous maintenance and updating
 - Rapidly evolving clinical landscape
 - Limited self life of items

Automatic Item Generation

- Overview of Automatic Item Generation (AIG)
 - Using computer algorithms to automatically create psychological test items
 - The concept was first raised by John Bormuth in the 1960s [2]
 - AIG became an intended research area in 2010s [4]
 - Rule-based [1], ML/DL architectures (e.g., RNN) [8-9], Encoder-based transformer models (e.g., BERT) [3]
 - For the past decade, research focused more on large scale generation[5]

Large Language Models (LLMs) for AIG

- A promising tool for AIG
 - Successful implementation in educational domains [6,7]
 - Flexibility and efficiency
- Research gaps
 - Limited focus on simple knowledge checks
 - Underexplored application of LLMs for high-stakes clinical assessment items
 - Lack of comparative analysis between automated and expert-written items
- ***RQ: How effective are LLMs in generating multiple choice items for high-stakes clinical assessment?***

Building a Clinical Scenario

- Challenges
 - Accuracy
 - Diversity
 - Distractor Functionality
 - Ecological validity

Proposed Pipeline Overview

Knowledge Seeds to Clinical Report

- **Seeds Generator** → knowledge seeds
 - Medical entities (e.g., disorder name, medication, biological structure)
 - biomedical-ner-all (Named Entity Recognition transformer model)
- **LLMs Researcher** → clinical report
 - A structured research report for the knowledge seeds
 - Paralleled LLM summary chains to generate individual report

Clinical Report to Items

- **LLMs Writer** → Multiple choice options
 - Categorizing cues into 4 levels of acuity (mild, moderate, severe, life-threatening)
 - Generating item options based on pre-defined option templates
 - Labeling the option as ***Expected manifestation*** or ***Needs immediate follow-up***
- **Item Assembler** → Item bank
 - A rule-based and iterative process

Generation Results

- 63 extracted knowledge seeds
 - Option bank with 394 options
 - 215 options with “Expected Manifestation” label
 - 179 options with “Needs immediate follow-up” label
 - Support generation up to 50 single MC items
 - It’s scalable
2. The nurse has been made aware of the following client situations. The nurse should first see the client with
 - A: herpes simplex who is receiving valacyclovir and has decreased platelet count
 - B: nephrotic syndrome who is receiving furosemide and reporting muscle cramps
 - C: gonorrhea who is reporting painful urination
 - D: angina who is receiving nitroglycerin and reporting severe headaches
 3. The nurse has received a change-of-shift report on four assigned clients. The nurse should first assess
 - A: 55-year-old client with cardiomyopathy who has chest pain
 - B: 55-year-old client with pyrosis who has elevated c-reactive protein levels
 - C: 55-year-old client with osteomalacia who has elevated alkaline phosphatase levels
 - D: 60-year-old client with lymphedema who has skin discoloration and difficulty fitting into clothes

Evaluation

- Item evaluation mixed pack
 - 20 items: 15 LLMs-generated items + 5 Expert-generated items
 - Two content experts performed the evaluation independently
- Item evaluation results

Item Type	LLMs-Generated Items			Experts-Generated Items		
	Ecological Validity	Plausible Distractor	Key	Ecological Validity	Plausible Distractor	Key
Rater 1	4.97	2.56	3/15 double keys	4.80	2.87	1/5 double keys
Rater 2	3.95	3.10	3/15 double keys	4.10	3.20	NA

Discussion

- Practical Implications
 - Facilitating MC item development for high-stakes clinical assessment
 - Allowing for more efficient updates to the item bank
- Limitations
 - Instruction following issue → quality of distractors and labeling of keys
 - Limited evaluation scope
- Future work
 - Improve the LLMs pipeline (Med-Gemini, graph RAG system, human-in-the-loop)
 - Further extensive evaluations (evaluation scales, more items, overall ecological validity)

Thank You!

Q&A

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